

Complexes of Some Platinum Metals with Imidazole and Benzimidazole.

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Complex compounds of Rh(III), Ir(III) and Pt(II) with imidazole (IzH), benzimidazole (BzH), 2-methylbenzimidazole (MBzH) and 2-guanidinobenzimidazole (GB) of the formulae $[ML_2X_2]X$ ($X=Cl, Br, I, NO_2$ or NCS ; if $M=Rh, L=IzH, BzH, MBzH$ and GB ; and when $M=Ir, L=BzH$ and GB only); $[M(GB)_2B_2]^{2+}$ ($M=Rh$ and Ir and $B=H_2O, NH_3, Py, \frac{1}{2}picolinate, \frac{1}{2}phen$ and $\frac{1}{2}dipy$), $[Tr(BzH)_2X_2(H_2O)]$ ($X=Cl, Br$ and I), $[Rh(bz)_2]3H_2O, [Rh(IzH)_2Cl_2]Cl, [PtL_2X_2]$ ($L=Iz, BzH, MBzH$ and $\frac{1}{2}GB$; and $X=Cl, Br, I, NCS$ and NO_2), $[Pt(GB)_2Cl_2]$ and $[Pt(IzH)_4]Cl_2$ have been prepared and characterised. The diacid complexes $[ML_2X_2]X$ of Rh(III) and Ir(III) with IzH, BzH and MBzH have ligand-bridged polymeric octahedral structure with trans bonding of acido groups. The diacid and hetero complexes of Rh(III) and Ir(III) with GB and the tetrakis complex $[Rh(IzH)_4Cl_2]Cl$ have mono nuclear cis configuration and the others are polymeric. With the exception of $[Pt(GB)_2X_2]$, the diacid complexes of Pt(II), have trans planar structure.

THE study of imidazole complexes with transition metal ions is of interest as the ligand is closely related with biological systems involving histidine residue. The formation and structural aspects of some transition metal complexes of imidazoles and benzimidazoles have been reported from this laboratory¹⁻¹⁰ and by various other workers¹¹⁻²¹. The extensive investigation on the complexing properties of imidazole, benzimidazole and their alkyl derivatives have shown that imidazole forms some of the most stable complexes of all heterocyclic-N ligands. This is supported by the high acid association constant of imidazole. The acidity of the hydrogen bound at the pyrrole nitrogen is very weak ($pK_a = 14.52$)²². It has also been found that the pyridine nitrogen rather than the imino nitrogen is the bonding site. The ionisation of the imino hydrogen changes the molecule to the bidentate imidazolate anion, which causes the formation of polymeric species¹³. In certain complexes neutral ligand coordinates as bidentate molecule forming bridges between two metal atoms. N.m.r. results on the ligand indicate that the pyrrole hydrogen exchanges with the nitrogen at the 3-position²³.

GB is an important benzimidazole derivative and forms six membered inner chelate ring like biguanide but due to conjugation from benzimidazole ring, the stability of complexes of GB is expected to be high. The complexes of GB with Co(II & III), Cr(III), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) have been reported from this laboratory⁷⁻⁹. In the present communication we are reporting the complexes of Rh(III) and Pt(II) with IzH, BzH, MBzH, and GB, and those of Ir(III) with BzH and GB. The ligands are represented by the following

structure :

IzH

Iz⁻

BzH

MBzH

GB

Results and Discussion

We have observed that imidazole, benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole fail to stabilize trivalent cobalt, but these ligands form quite stable complexes with trivalent rhodium and iridium.

From the results of elemental analyses it is found that with imidazole, rhodium(III) forms complexes containing either four ligand molecules $[Rh(IzH)_4Cl_2]Cl$ or two ligand molecules $[Rh(IzH)_2X_2]X$ ($X=Cl, Br, I, NO_2$ and NCS). The tetrakis complex is formed at higher pH (4-5) but the bis complex $[Rh(IzH)_2Cl_2]Cl$ at low pH (2-3). It appears that at lower pH the effective electroneutrality can be maintained better by the ligated chloride ion. The tetrakis complex chloride $[Rh(IzH)_4Cl_2]Cl$, is fairly soluble in water, ethanol, DMF, and

dioxane but the bis complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ are almost insoluble in water and common organic solvents. In DMF they however, dissolve slightly on warming. The insolubility of the bis complexes indicate that they are probably polymeric and the polymer appears to break up in warm DMF. The preferred octahedral geometry of rhodium(III), in $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ can be achieved either by imidazole or by the acido groups behaving as bidentate. Since other diacido derivatives are conveniently obtained from the dichloro complex by substitution reactions, the imidazole must be behaving as a bridging ligand between two rhodium atoms. Such behaviour of IzH has been found by X-ray analysis of zinc imidazolate¹⁴.

A freshly prepared aqueous solution of the tetrakis complex, $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, exhibits molar conductance value expected for 1 : 1 electrolytes (Table - A). The electrical conductance value, however, increases gradually probably due to aquation. The DMF solution of the bis complexes are also conducting; and the molar conductance values ($50-75 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) lie within the acceptable range of 1 : 1 electrolyte type²⁶. Electrical conductance values of some of the complexes, indicate that at least one acido group per rhodium atom is ionic.

The electronic absorption spectra of aqueous solution of $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ displays a weak absorption at 328 nm attributable to ${}^1\text{A}_g \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ transition²⁶ and a strong absorption below 300 nm. The electronic absorption spectra of DMF solution of the complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ do not exhibit any distinct transition rather these show strong charge transfer absorption below 350 nm.

Unlike imidazole, benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole form only bis complexes, $[\text{Rh}(\text{L}_2\text{X}_2)]\text{X}$ ($\text{L} = \text{BzH}$ and MBzH , and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, Br , I , NO_2 and NCS). The chlorine atoms of dichloro complexes undergo substitution reaction by donor groups like NCS , NO_2 , Br and I in aqueous solution forming diacido complexes $[\text{RhL}_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Br}$, I , NCS and NO_2). These complexes, in general, are insoluble in water or ethanol but slightly dissolve in DMF and pyridine. The molar conductance values of the complexes at room temperature fall in the range of 1 : 1 electrolyte type (Table A). Like bis (imidazole) complexes, these complexes also appear to be polymeric with octahedral geometry having nonacido bridged structure. The polymer appears to be cleaved in polar solvents. The electronic absorption spectra do not display distinct d-d band; reflectance spectra of the complexes, however, show weak band or shoulder between 432 and 475 nm (Table A). The position of these, follows the order of the positions of these anions in the spectrochemical series : $\text{NO}_2 > \text{NCS} > \text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{I}$.

$[\text{Rh}(\text{BzH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ when suspended in water and refluxed undergoes aquation forming $[\text{Rh}(\text{BzH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_3$. Like the diacido complexes, it is insoluble in water and common organic solvents; but slightly soluble in hot DMF. Molar conductance value in DMF ($\sim 232 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ ohm}^{-1}$) indicates that the

complex is 1 : 3 electrolyte type. The tris chelated inner complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{Bz})_3]3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is formed at pH 8-9 in presence of excess of the ligand. The compound is almost insoluble in water but is slightly soluble in hot DMF. As expected, the DMF solution is non conducting. The insolubility of the complex indicates that the complex is polymeric.

The diacido iridium(III) complexes, $[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, Br , NCS , I and NO_2), like the rhodium analogues $[\text{Rh}(\text{BzH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$, could be prepared by refluxing the reactants, but take much longer time for formation. The lower rate of substitution is as expected, for Ir(III) complexes towards substitution reaction. The complexes have lower solubility in DMF compared to their rhodium analogues. The electrical conductance of the complexes could not be made accurately for want of suitable solvent, however, qualitative values of Ω_m of the complexes (Table A) in the DMF indicate some ionic nature.

Unlike rhodium(III), iridium(III) forms a complex of formula, $[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})\text{X}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}]_n$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br) at higher acid concentration (pH 1-2). These have poor solubility, even in DMF, suggesting their polymeric nature. Attempts to prepare the thiocyanato and nitro analogue of $[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})\text{X}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ like $[\text{IrL}_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{NCS}$ and NO_2) were unsuccessful. This indicates that BzH as well as some halogen atoms are bonded as bridging groups. The electrical absorption or reflectance spectra of these complexes were found to be of little significance for deciding the stereochemistry of the complexes since they only display charge transfer absorption.

With GB, Rh (III) forms bis-, tris- as well as hetero-complexes of the types $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, Br , I , NO_2 and NCS), $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_3]\text{X}_3$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or ClO_4) and $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2\text{B}_2]^{m+}$ ($\text{B} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$, NH_3 , Py , $\frac{1}{2}$ dipy, $\frac{1}{2}$ phen and $\frac{1}{2}$ α -picolinate) respectively. However, with iridium(III) only bischelated stable complexes $[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, Br , I , NCS and NO_2) and hetero complexes $[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2\text{B}_2]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where $\text{B} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$, NH_3 , Py , $\frac{1}{2}$ dipy and $\frac{1}{2}$ phen) have been isolated. The yellow diaquo complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is formed on refluxing a mixture of an aqueous solution of $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 mole) and GB (2 moles) at pH 2-3. Under identical reaction conditions, imidazole and benzimidazole form polymeric dichloro complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{Iz})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$. The dichloro bis-(2-guanidinobenzimidazole) Rh(III) nitrate, $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{NO}_3$, is obtained on the addition of a few drops of conc. HNO_3 to the diaquo complex (pH 1-2) and chilling it to ice temperature. The dichloro complex chloride $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ could not be isolated directly. However, it was obtained by thermal effect from diaquo chloride $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 160° . The thermogravimetric analysis of $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicated that uncoordinated H_2O is lost below 80° , while coordinated water between 140 and 160° . The resulting chloro complex is decomposed slowly to Rh_2O_3 between $333-330^\circ$. It was found that coordinated water molecules of diaquo complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ undergo substitution reaction by donor bases like

TABLE—A

Complex	Colour	λ_{m} $\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ mole^{-1}	% Metal Found (Required)	% Nitrogen Found (Required)	Absorption band (in nm)
[Rh(IzH) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	Cream	115	21.43 (21.35)	23.41 (23.27)	328 α
[Rh(IzH) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	Brick red	73	29.96 (29.80)	16.07 (16.02)	—
[Rh(IzH) ₂ Br ₂]Br	Light brown	58	21.46 (21.51)	11.58 (11.60)	—
[Rh(IzH) ₂ I ₂]I	Dark brown	50	16.59 (16.61)	9.10 (9.03)	—
[Rh(IzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	White	—	27.30 (27.32)	29.70 (29.96)	—
[Rh(IzH) ₂ (NCS) ₂]NCS	Orange yellow	—	24.92 (24.93)	23.67 (23.72)	—
[Rh(BzH) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	Brick red	82	23.10 (23.12)	12.51 (12.57)	462
[Rh(BzH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Light yellow	232	21.35 (21.39)	11.71 (11.63)	450
[Rh(BzH) ₂ Br ₂]Br	Light brown	79	17.77 (17.79)	9.63 (9.67)	468
[Rh(BzH) ₂ I ₂]I	Dark brown	75	14.30 (14.32)	7.73 (7.78)	478
[Rh(BzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	White	73	21.47 (21.59)	20.41 (20.54)	432
[Rh(BzH) ₂ (NCS) ₂]SCN	Orange yellow	68	20.02 (20.07)	19.06 (19.10)	444
[Rh(Bz) ₂]3H ₂ O	Light yellow	—	20.17 (20.27)	16.45 (16.54)	420
[Rh(MBzH) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	Red	50	21.79 (21.77)	11.78 (11.76)	460
[Rh(MBzH) ₂ Br ₂]Br	Light brown	—	16.77 (16.95)	9.27 (9.22)	470
[Rh(MBzH) ₂ I ₂]I	Deep brown	40	13.61 (13.58)	7.38 (7.39)	478 sh
[Rh(MBzH) ₂ (NCS) ₂]SCN	Orange yellow	—	19.02 (19.01)	18.13 (18.10)	—
[Rh(MBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	White	—	20.39 (20.37)	19.31 (19.40)	363 (ϵ_{max} 132) α
[Rh(GB) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	Yellow	212 a	10.73 (10.84)	25.01 (25.13)	368 (ϵ_{max} 223) α
[Rh(GB) ₂ Br ₂]Br	Bright yellow	115 a	14.74 (14.85)	20.28 (20.21)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ Cl ₂]NO ₂ .4H ₂ O	Yellow	—	15.61 (15.64)	23.51 (23.40)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ I ₂]I	Brown	—	12.28 (12.34)	16.99 (16.79)	379 (ϵ_{max} 1305) α
[Rh(GB) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	Light yellow	102 a	17.71 (17.80)	30.86 (30.79)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ (NCS) ₂]NCS	Orange yellow	—	16.38 (16.41)	29.17 (29.02)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	Dull yellow	368 a	16.91 (16.71)	22.87 (22.82)	346 sh α
[Rh(GB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₂) ₂ . 4H ₂ O	Orange yellow	—	13.65 (13.77)	24.47 (24.36)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂]Cl ₂	White	406 a	17.45 (17.33)	28.27 (28.31)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ Py ₂]Cl ₂	White	—	14.48 (14.38)	23.38 (23.41)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ pic]Cl ₂ .3H ₂ O	Pale yellow	271 a	14.57 (14.69)	22.11 (22.00)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ pic]SO ₄ .4H ₂ O	Pale yellow	—	13.72 (13.84)	20.67 (20.72)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ dipy]Cl ₂	Straw	411 a	14.28 (14.38)	23.31 (23.48)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ dipy]I ₂	Cream yellow	—	10.56 (10.39)	16.88 (16.97)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ (o-phen)]Cl ₂	Straw	403 a	14.17 (13.91)	22.52 (22.71)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂ (o-phen)]I ₂	Cream yellow	—	10.36 (10.15)	16.41 (16.57)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂]Cl ₂	Straw	411 a	14.12 (14.01)	28.68 (28.59)	—
[Rh(GB) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	Pale yellow	—	11.08 (11.10)	22.45 (22.67)	—

(Contd.)

(Table A Contd)

Complexes	Colour	Δm $\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ mole^{-1}	% Metal Found (Required)	% Nitrogen Found (Required)	Absorption band (in nm)
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})\text{Cl}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Light brown	—	44 53 (44 31)	6 48 (6 42)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})\text{Br}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Dull brown	—	33 61 (33 93)	5 01 (4 92)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})\text{I}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Dark brown	—	27 24 (27 19)	3 91 (3 94)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Light yellow	53	36 08 (36 04)	10 51 (10 45)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})_2\text{Br}_2]\text{Br}$	Light brown	43	28 84 (28 84)	8 37 (8 38)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})_2\text{I}_2]\text{I}$	Dull brown	48	23 92 (23 82)	6 98 (6 91)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{SCN}$	Light yellow	—	32 10 (32 10)	16 28 (16 25)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_2$	Cream yellow	—	34 08 (34 04)	17 32 (17 28)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Light yellow	98 a	29 53 (29 61)	21 75 (21 58)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{ClO}_4$	Light yellow	—	—	19 45 (19 65)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2\text{Br}_2]\text{Br}$	Dull yellow	93 a	24 11 (24 32)	18 08 (17 90)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2(\text{I}_2)]\text{I}$	Dull Brown	—	—	15 03 (15 17)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_2$	Light yellow	—	27 80 (27 97)	26 90 (26 75)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{SCN}$	Light yellow	—	—	25 31 (25 40)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Greenish yellow	333 a	26 77 (26 65)	19 71 (19 43)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2(\text{Py})]_2\text{Cl}_2$	Pale yellow	380 a	23 98 (23 81)	20 76 (20 82)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{Cl}_2$	White	369 a	28 32 (28 14)	24 35 (24 61)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2 \text{dipy}]\text{Cl}_2$	White	401 a	—	20 64 (20 87)	
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2 \text{o-phen}]\text{Cl}_2$	White	395 a	—	20 10 (20 27)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_4]\text{Cl}_2$	Cream white	198 b	36 37 (36,25)	20 64 (20 81)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	Cream yellow	—	48 38 (48 53)	14 01 (13 93)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_2\text{Br}_2]$	Cream yellow	8	39 64 (39 73)	11 30 (11 40)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_2\text{I}_2]$	Orange	—	33 42 (33 34)	9 64 (9 57)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$	Orange yellow	—	43 56 (43 63)	18 87 (18 78)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	Cream white	—	46 21 (46 11)	17 51 (17 48)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{BzH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	Cream yellow	7	38 79 (38 85)	11 27 (11 15)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{BzH})_2\text{Br}_2]$	Cream yellow	—	33 13 (33 01)	9 58 (9 47)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{BzH})_2\text{I}_2]$	Orange yellow	—	28 51 (28 48)	8 21 (8 17)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{BzH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$	Light yellow	—	35 67 (35 66)	15 42 (15 36)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{BzH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	Cream white	—	37 13 (37 29)	15 94 (16 06)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{MBzH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	Cream yellow	—	36 78 (36 80)	10 51 (10 56)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{MBzH})_2\text{Br}_2]$	Cream yellow	7	31 51 (31 52)	8 98 (9 05)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{MBzH})_2\text{I}_2]$	Light yellow	5	27 32 (27 36)	7 86 (7 85)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{MBzH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$	Light yellow	—	34 02 (33,91)	14 74 (14 61)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{MBzH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	Cream white	—	53 46 (53 39)	15 31 (15 24)	
$[\text{Pt}(\text{GB})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Cream yellow	198 a	31 83 (31 65)	22 76 (22 72)	

(Contd)

(Table A Contd.)

Complex	Colour	Λ_m Ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	% metal Found (Required)	% Nitrogen Found (Required)	Absorption band (in nm)
[Pt(GB)Cl ₂]	Dull yellow	6	44.21 (44.23)	15.91 (15.87)	
[Pt(GB)Br ₂]	Dull yellow	7	36.91 (36.81)	13.31 (13.21)	
[Pt(GB)I ₂]	Light brown	—	31.31 (31.24)	11.21 (11.20)	
[Pt(GB)(NCS) ₂]	Cream yellow	—	40.24 (40.14)	20.21 (20.16)	
[Pt(GB)(NO ₂) ₂]	Light cream	—	42.31 (42.22)	21.31 (21.20)	

a=Conductance or absorption spectra in aqueous solution.

The estimation of halogen or sulphate groups in the complexes agree with the required value.

NH₃, Py, dipy or *o*-phen and donor anions Br, I, NO₂, NCS and picolinate, forming hetero and diacido complexes: [Rh(GB)₂B₂]X_n·nH₂O (B = NH₃, Py, $\frac{1}{2}$ dipy and $\frac{1}{2}$ phen) and [Rh(GB)₂X₂]X (X = Br, I, NO₂ and NCS) respectively. The case of substitution of water molecules by bidentate chelating molecules like *o*-phen, dipy and α -picolinate ion suggests that diaquo complex has probably cis structure. From the analogy, the complexes prepared from diaquo chloride, [Rh(GB)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₃ are also anticipated to possess the cis structure. Electronic absorption spectra of the complexes (Table—A) exhibit large ϵ_{max} values; which may be indicative of the cis configuration of these Rh(III) complexes.

The electronic absorption spectrum of an aqueous solution of [Rh(GB)₂Cl₂]Cl shows a gradual shift in λ_{max} from 363 nm to 346 nm (in 4 hrs.) indicating the aquation of the complex at room temperature. The molar conductance value (212 ohm⁻¹ mole⁻¹ cm²) of an aqueous solution of [Rh(GB)₂Cl₂]Cl suggests the existence of an equilibrium:

It was found that hydrochloric acid solution of Ir(III) (pH 4—5) on refluxing with stoichiometric proportion of GB, yielded greenish yellow diaquo complex [Ir(GB)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₃. The dichloro complex, [Ir(GB)₂Cl₂]Cl could be obtained on refluxing an aqueous solution of Ir(III) chloride in presence of a large excess of sodium chloride. The coordinated water as well as the chlorine atom in the bischelated complexes [Ir(GB)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₃·2H₂O and [Ir(GB)₂Cl₂]Cl, like rhodium analogues, are conveniently replaced by strong donor groups like NO₂, NCS, NH₃, Py, dipy or *o*-phen forming hetero complexes [Ir(GB)₂B₂]ⁿ⁺ (B = NO₂, NCS, NH₃, Py, $\frac{1}{2}$ dipy or $\frac{1}{2}$ phen and n=1 or 3).

The dihalo complexes [Ir(GB)₂X₂] (X = Br or I) are obtained by warming [Ir(GB)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₃ with the

appropriate halogen hydric acids. These are generally soluble in water and their aqueous solutions exhibit molar conductance values in the range expected for 1 : 1 electrolyte type.

Unlike Pd(II), which forms tetrakis as well as diacido complexes with BzH and MBzH, Pt(II) forms only diacido complexes [PtL₂X₂] (X = Cl, Br, I, NO₂ and NCS; and L = BzH and MBzH). The dichloro complexes, [PtL₂Cl₂], are readily prepared by refluxing and concentrating an acidic solution of Pt(II) chloride (pH = 3—4) with the desired ligand. The other diacido complexes are obtained by usual substitution reaction of the dichloro complexes in aqueous solution. Unlike benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole, imidazole forms bis as well as tetrakis complexes, [Pt(IzH)₂X₂] (X = Cl, Br, I, NCS and NO₂) and [Pt(IzH)₄]Cl₂ with bivalent Pt. In case of benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole the tetrakis complexes could not be formed probably due to greater steric volume of the ligands. The tetrakis imidazole complex is soluble in water and molar conductance value (198 ohm⁻¹ at 28°) is as expected from the stoichiometry. The DMF solutions of the diacido complexes [PtL₂X₂] (L = IzH, BzH and MBzH) is almost nonconducting showing them to be nonelectrolytes. The electronic absorption spectra of Pt(II) complexes display only strong absorption below 350 nm and, therefore, no inference can be made.

The infrared spectra of Rh(III), Ir(III) and Pt(II) complexes have been proved to be useful in deciding the nature of bonding and configuration of complexes for diacido complexes. Except a few dihalo complexes, the i.r. spectra of the complexes were recorded in the range 650—4000 cm⁻¹.

Among the various infrared vibrations of imidazole and benzimidazole molecules, the studies of the NH and C=N vibrations have been found to be useful for deciding the site of coordinations of the ligand molecules. Free imidazole displays N—H stretching band

at 3320 cm^{-1} and N-H deformation at 1548 cm^{-1} . The C=N stretch of the imidazole is observed at 1582 cm^{-1} . It is found that the position of $\nu(\text{N-H})$ and $\delta(\text{N-H})$ vibrations are not affected appreciably in tetrakis complexes, $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_4]\text{Cl}_2$ and diacido complexes $[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_2\text{X}_2]$, while the $\nu(\text{C=N})$ vibration is raised to higher frequency and observed at $1605 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The shift of $\nu(\text{C=N})$ band in these tetrakis complexes indicate the bonding of imidazole through the tertiary nitrogen atom only. The bis imidazole complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl, Br, I, NO}_2$ and NCS) displays NH stretching band at 3210 ± 20 , $\delta(\text{N-H})$ at $1545 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu(\text{CN})$ vibration at $1605 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The decrease of $\nu(\text{N-H})$ and increase in $\nu(\text{C=N})$ vibrations indicate that the pyrrole as well as the tertiary nitrogen of imidazole ring is involved in coordination in $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$. Thus, the i.r. spectra of diacido bis imidazole complexes supports the bidentate coordination of imidazole molecule in diacido bis imidazole complexes. Had the imidazole molecule been coordinated to rhodium atom as bidentate chelating group, the diacido bis chelates $[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ should be mononuclear and should have been soluble in polar solvents, which is not the case. Imidazole molecules, therefore are bridging two rhodium atoms forming polymers.

The (C=N) stretching band of benzimidazole (1600 cm^{-1}) and 2-methylbenzimidazole (1596 cm^{-1}) shift to higher frequency by 20 ± 5 for Pt(II) as well as Rh(III) and Ir(III) complexes, suggesting that tertiary nitrogen of benzimidazoles is one of the bonding sites of the ligand. Except Pt(II) complexes $[\text{PtL}_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{L}=\text{BzH}$ or MBzH and $\text{X}=\text{Cl, Br, I, NO}_2$ and NCS), the (N-H) stretching frequencies of benzimidazole (3248 cm^{-1}) as well as 2-methylbenzimidazole (3218 cm^{-1}) are shifted to lower frequency by $50 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in almost all the complexes of rhodium(III) and iridium(III). Thus, it is inferred that benzimidazole as well as 2-methylbenzimidazole, like imidazole, are coordinated to rhodium(III) and iridium(III) through the pyrrole as well as tertiary nitrogen of imidazole nucleus. The i.r. spectra of GB, as well as its complexes, display benzimidazole ring NH stretching vibration at the same frequency ($3360 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), indicating that pyrrole nitrogen of benzimidazole is not involved in coordination. The $\nu(\text{C=N})$ stretching band of guanidine part of the ligand located at 1680 cm^{-1} shifts to lower frequency in its complexes by $20 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Thus, it may be inferred that GB is coordinated to metal atoms through tertiary nitrogen of benzimidazole part and =NH nitrogen of guanidine part like biguanide²⁴. The i.r. spectra of some dichloro complex of Rh(III) and Ir(III) with GB displays two M-Cl

stretching vibrations, but dichloro benzimidazole complexes only one (Table-B). Therefore, dichloro complexes with GB has been assigned cis while those with benzimidazole trans configuration²⁷.

The $\nu(\text{CN})$ and $\nu(\text{C=S})$ band of dithiocyanato complexes are recorded in Table-C.

TABLE-C

Complexes	$\nu(\text{CN})$ in cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{C=S})$ in cm^{-1}
$[\text{Rh}(\text{IzH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{SCN}$	2100 vs	756 m
$[\text{Rh}(\text{BzH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{SCN}$	2095 vs	768 m
$[\text{Rh}(\text{MBzH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{SCN}$	2105 vs	758 m
$[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{SCN}$	2086 vs 2055m	817 w 771 w
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{SCN}$	2100 sbr 2048m	768 w
$[\text{I}(\text{GB})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{SCN}$	2093 vs 2048m	809 m
$[\text{Pt}(\text{GB})(\text{NCS})_2]$	2100 sbr	822m
$[\text{Pt}(\text{IzH})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	2104 s. sp	690 w
$[\text{Pt}(\text{BzH})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	2122 s. sp	720 w
$[\text{Pt}(\text{MBzH})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	2125 s. sp	710 w

The i. r. spectra of the thiocyanato complexes could not be recorded in $\delta(\text{NCS})$ region; however, from the frequency and the nature of $\nu(\text{CN})$ and $\nu(\text{C=S})$ vibrations in these complexes, the site of bonding of NCS groups have been suggested. Except $[\text{Pt}(\text{GB})(\text{NCS})_2]$, the dithiocyanato Pt(II) complexes display $\nu(\text{CN})$ as strong and sharp bands between 2118 and 2125 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{CS})$ as weak bands between 690 and 720 cm^{-1} . The observed frequency range and sharpness of $\nu(\text{CN})$ and $\nu(\text{CS})$ vibrations are characteristics of sulphur bonded thiocyanate groups²⁸. Other thiocyanato complexes (Table-C) display $\nu(\text{CN})$ vibrations as broad and very strong bands between $2086-2105 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu(\text{CS})$ vibrations ($756-822 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) as weak and medium bands. The $\nu(\text{CN})$ vibration has been found to split up into two bands in the GB complexes. Thus, it is suggested that thiocyanate group is bonded to metals in cis position through nitrogen atoms in GB complexes.

The i.r. frequencies in cm^{-1} of dinitro complexes of imidazole, benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole (Table-D) do not display splitting of $\delta(\text{ONO})$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{NO}_2)$ vibrations analogous to cis bonded nitro complexes²⁹. In the i. r. spectrum of GB complexes $[\text{M}(\text{GB})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ NO_2 and $[\text{Pt}(\text{GB})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ an additional $\nu_{as}(\text{NO}_2)$ and $\delta(\text{ONO})$ bands are observed.

Thus, it is inferred that nitro groups have cis bonding in GB complexes but trans in imidazole and benzimidazole complexes²⁹. From the above discussion we arrive at the conclusion that diacido complexes $[\text{ML}_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$, $\text{L}=\text{Iz, BzH}$ or MBz ; and $\text{M}=\text{Rh(III)}$ and Ir(III) , have ligand bridged polymeric chain structure with trans bonding of acido groups.

TABLE-B

Complexes	$\nu(\text{M-Cl})$
$[\text{Rh}(\text{GB})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	333s, 296m
$[\text{Ir}(\text{GB})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	310m, 291m
$[\text{Rh}(\text{BzH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	329m
$[\text{Ir}(\text{BzH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	317m

TABLE—D

Complexes	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$	$\delta(\text{ONO})$
[Rh(IzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	1398 s. bs	1319 s	821 m
[Rh(BzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	1400 s	1319 s	825 m
[Rh(MBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	1390 s. br	1320 s	824 m
[Rh(GB) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	1395 s.	1341 s	833 m
[Ir(GB) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	1391 s.	1319 m	827 m
[Ir(BzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂	1390 s	1349 s	834 m
		1319 s	829 m
		1320 s	824 m
[Pt(IzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	1404 s	1338 s	829 s
[Pt(BzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	1412 s. br	1316 s. br	830 m
[Pt(MBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	1416 s. br	1312 s	827 s
[Pt(GB) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	1370 s	1327 s	829 s
		1305 sh	817 m

s = strong ; br = broad ; and sh = shoulder.

Experimental

Materials : Hydrated IrCl₃, RhCl₃ and (NH₄)₂IrCl₆, were obtained from Fluka, Switzerland and Chloroplatinic acid from Johnson Mathey Chemicals, London. Platinum (II) chloride was prepared from chloroplatinic acid according to method given by Brauer^{8,9}. Imidazole was obtained from Fluka and was used without further purification. Benzimidazole, 2-methylbenzimidazole and 2-guanidinobenzimidazole were prepared as described in literature^{1,7}. Physical measurements were made as reported in our earlier communication⁶.

[Rh(L₂Cl₂)Cl] (L = IzH, BzH and MBzH) : An ethanolic solution of RhCl₃·3H₂O (0.5 g in 50 ml ethanol + few drops of HCl) was refluxed with the ligand (1 : 2 molar ratio), on a steam bath, for about half an hour. The brick red dichloro complex was isolated by concentrating the refluxed solution to a small volume. The product was collected on a filter, washed with ethanol and dried in air.

[RhL₂X₂]X (L = IzH, BzH and MBzH ; and X = Br, I, NO₂ and NCS) : The dichloro complex [RhL₂Cl₂]Cl, was suspended in water (0.5 g in 200 ml) and refluxed with excess of sodium or potassium salts of appropriate anion on a steam bath for 2–3 hrs. The refluxed solution was filtered hot and the filtrate on concentration yielded the desired diacido complexes. The products were washed with cold water, ethanol and dried in air.

[Rh(BzH)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₂ : The aqueous suspension of dichloro complex, [Rh(BzH)₂Cl₂]Cl undergoes aqution on boiling producing the diaquo complex [Rh(BzH)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₂. The complex was isolated as light yellow product on concentrating the solution to a small volume.

[Rh(IzH)₄Cl₂]Cl : An ethanolic solution of the hydrated Rh(III) chloride (0.5 g in 100 ml) was refluxed with excess of imidazole (0.65 g, about 1 : 5 molar ratio) on a steam bath till the solution became colourless. The refluxate was concentrated to a small volume

and cooled in ice when cream coloured crystal of tetrakis complex chloride separated.

[Ir(BzH)X₃(H₂O)] (X = Cl, Br, I) : An aqueous solution of hydrated iridium trichloride (2%) acidified with excess of conc. halo hydracids (pH 1–2) was refluxed with molar proportion of ethanolic solution of BzH when the mono benzimidazole complexes [Ir(BzH)X₃(H₂O)] separated. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in air.

[Ir(BzH)₂Cl₂]Cl : An aqueous solution of hydrated iridium trichloride (0.4 g in 40 ml) was refluxed with an ethanolic solution of the ligand (1 : 2 molar ratio) for about four hours. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted between 3 and 4, and then concentrated to a small volume when light yellow crystals of the dichloro complex separated. The product was collected on a filter, washed with ethanol and dried in air.

[Ir(BzH)₂X₂]X (X = Br, I, NO₂ and NCS) : These were obtained from the dichloro complex [Ir(BzH)₂Cl₂]Cl, in the same way as mentioned in case of [RhL₂X₂]X above.

[Pt(IzH)₄]Cl₂ : An aqueous solution of Pt(II) chloride (0.5g in 50 ml) was treated with excess of imidazole (1:5 molar ratio) and refluxed on a steam bath for an hour. The refluxate was filtered and the filtrate (pH 6–7) on concentration and cooling, yielded crystals of the tetrakis complex.

[PtL₂Cl₂] (L = IzH, BzH and MBzH) : An aqueous acidic solution of Pt(II) chloride (pH 2–3) was refluxed with requisite amount of ethanolic solution of the appropriate ligand for an hour. The solution, on concentration, deposited cream coloured crystals of the dichloro complexes [PtL₂Cl₂]. The products were collected, washed with cold water and ethanol and then dried in air.

[PtL₂X₂] (L = IzH, BzH and MBzH ; and X = Br, I, NCS and NO₂) : These were obtained by refluxing an aqueous suspension of the dichloro complex with two molar proportion of sodium or potassium salts of appropriate anions for about 2 hours. On concentrating the refluxate, the desired diacido complexes separated. The products were filtered, washed with cold water and ethanol and dried in air.

[Pt(GB)₂]Cl₂ : An aqueous solution of Pt(II) chloride was refluxed with ethanolic solution GB in 1 : 2 molar ratio, (pH 5–6). On processing like tetrakis (imidazole) platinum (II) chloride, the bischelated complex chloride was obtained.

[Pt(GB)Cl₂] : The dichloro complex was obtained as a cream yellow product when an acidic solution of Pt(II) chloride (pH 2-3) was refluxed with ethanolic solution of the ligand in 1 : 1 molar proportion.

$[Pt(GB)X_2]$ ($X=Br, I, NCS$ and NO_2): These diacido complexes were obtained by following a procedure similar to that used for the corresponding diacido complexes of Pt(II) with benzimidazole. The products were filtered, washed with cold water, ethanol and dried in air.

$[Rh(GB)_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3 \cdot H_2O$: An aqueous solution of $RhCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ and ligand hydrochloride, in 1 : 2 molar ratio, was refluxed on a steam bath till an orange yellow solution was obtained. The solution was filtered hot and the filtrate was concentrated to a small volume when dull yellow precipitate of the diaquo complex separated. The product was filtered, washed with cold water, and dried in air. The complex nitrate $[Rh(GB)_2 \cdot (H_2O)_2](NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, was obtained by metathesis of $[Rh(GB)_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3 \cdot H_2O$ with dilute $AgNO_3$ solution.

$[Rh(GB)_2Cl_2]NO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$: When the above refluxate (from which the diaquo complex was isolated) was acidified with a few ml of conc. HNO_3 (pH 1-2) and chilled to ice temperature, the yellow dichloro complex separated as the nitrate salt. Dichloro complex $[Rh(GB)_2Cl_2]Cl$ was obtained by heating the diaquo complex $[Rh(GB)_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3 \cdot H_2O$ at $160^\circ C$ for 2 hours.

$[Rh(GB)_2X_2]X$ ($X=Br, I, NO_2$ and NCS): These were prepared by refluxing an aqueous solution of $[Rh(GB)_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3 \cdot H_2O$ with excess of sodium/potassium salts of appropriate anions, for about 2 hours. The solution was filtered and the filtrate, on concentration and cooling, deposited the desired diacido complexes $[Rh(GB)_2X_2]X$.

$[Rh(GB)_2B_2]Cl_3$ ($B=Py$ or NH_3): The diaquo complex $[Rh(GB)_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3 \cdot H_2O$ was refluxed with a few ml of dry pyridine (or conc. NH_3). A white residue was obtained when excess solvent was evaporated out. This was dissolved in dry ethanol and the pure compound precipitated on treatment with dry ether. The product was filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuum desiccator over KOH.

$[Rh(GB)_2B_2]Cl_n$ ($B_2 = \alpha$ -picolinate, α , α -dipy and $-o$ phen and $n=2$ or 3): An aqueous solution of $[Rh(GB)_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3 \cdot H_2O$ was refluxed with stoichiometric proportion of the desired ligand at $pH \sim 7$ (pH was raised slowly by adding dil. KOH) for two hours. The refluxate on concentration and cooling deposited the chloride of the desired mixed chelate. If the refluxate is concentrated after adding excess of KI or $(NH_4)_2SO_4$, the iodide or sulphate derivative of the complex was separated. These mixed chelates were purified by recrystallising from hot water.

$[Rh(GB)_3]Cl_3$: An aqueous solution of hydrated $RhCl_3$ was refluxed with stoichiometric proportion of GB for about 3 hrs, when a pale yellow solution resulted. This on concentration and cooling, deposited pale yellow crystals of the tris chelate, $[Rh(GB)_3]Cl_3$. If the refluxate is concentrated in presence of $NaClO_4$,

the sparingly soluble complex perchlorate separates as pale yellow crystals. The products were filtered, washed with a few drops of ethanol, ether and dried in air.

$[Ir(GB)_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3 \cdot 2H_2O$: An aqueous solution of $(NH_4)_2IrCl_6$ was reduced by boiling with oxalic acid (2 : 1 mole) and the reduced solution was refluxed with ligand hydrochloride at pH 4-5 for 3 hrs. The resulting orange red solution on concentration deposited greenish yellow precipitate of diaquo complex $[Ir(GB)_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3 \cdot 2H_2O$. The product was filtered, washed with water, ethanol, ether and dried in air.

$[Ir(GB)_2Cl_2]Cl$: The dichloro complex was obtained as light yellow precipitate, if the reduced solution of $(NH_4)_2IrCl_6$ is refluxed with ligand hydrochloride in presence of a large excess of NaCl (5 fold) for six hrs. and then concentrated. The dichloro complex perchlorate $[Ir(GB)_2Cl_2]ClO_4$ was obtained as yellow crystals when an aqueous solution of $[Ir(GB)_2Cl_2]Cl$ (0.3 g in 30 ml) was treated with 2 ml conc. $HClO_4$.

$[Ir(GB)_2X_2]X$ ($X=Br, I, NO_2$ or NCS) and $[Ir(GB)_2B_2]Cl_3$ ($B=NH_3, Py, \frac{1}{2}\alpha, \alpha$ -dipy or $\frac{1}{2}$ -o-phen): These hetero complexes of iridium were prepared using similar procedure as adopted for the corresponding Rh(III) analogues.

The analytical results, colour, molar conductance values (Λ_m) and electronic reflectance or absorption bands of some complexes are recorded in Table-A.

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